

APPLICATION OF THE PRINCIPLE OF CONTINUITY IN TEACHING MOLECULAR PHYSICS, STATISTICAL PHYSICS AND QUANTUM PHYSICS

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Abstract. *This article explains the importance of developing probabilistic-statistical skills to ensure the consistency of probabilistic-statistical concepts and the formation of ideas when teaching molecular physics and quantum statistics as part of the physics course based on the principle of continuity.*

Keywords: *innovation, competence, statistical physics, quantum physics, microphenomenon, microobject, principle of continuity.*

Introduction. Effective research is being conducted worldwide to improve the quality of physics teaching by integrating innovative information technologies and leveraging the potential of educational tools in the learning process. This aims to develop students' intellectual potential and creative abilities, as well as to create modern methodological support for professional fields based on the competency-based approach, ultimately ensuring the quality of education. Graduates of higher educational institutions must not only possess in-depth knowledge in all aspects but also adapt to the times by advancing their professional levels through scientific achievements [1].

One of the critical and essential conditions for the continuous professional development of individuals is consistency in learning. However, insufficient attention to ensuring consistency in students' academic activities during physics studies, as well as the unexplored potential for improving the implementation of the principle of consistency in education, often leads to the knowledge and skills acquired by students at various stages of learning being formed in a disconnected, chaotic, scattered, and discrete manner.

As a result of practical work carried out in creating opportunities for organizing the educational system in our country—through profound reforms, the establishment of organizational and pedagogical conditions, material and technical resources, qualified personnel, and the widespread use of advanced international practices—there has been significant implementation of innovative educational technologies in the learning process [2].

In light of modern didactic requirements, this situation necessitates expanding the general didactic potential of physics education by developing methods for teaching knowledge and skills in physics courses based on the principle of continuity within higher education systems. In other words, developing teaching methods enhanced by innovative technologies, allowing students to independently find mechanisms for establishing connections between the essence of topics taught in physics courses, and thus forming a scientific understanding of the continuous development of physics as a science, is one of today's urgent tasks. Consequently, organizing continuous education, which ensures the practical application of continuity principles at all learning stages, is among the key strategic directions of modern higher education [3].

Teaching sections of statistical physics and quantum physics in higher education plays a vital role in shaping students' scientific worldview. Ensuring continuity in organizing, activating,

and conducting their learning activities, particularly at the introductory stages of physics, by harmonizing topics such as molecular physics and quantum statistics taught at advanced levels, remains underdeveloped in terms of didactic tools and teaching methods. This results in a fragmented understanding of physical laws without establishing their interconnections [4].

The necessity of emphasizing the importance of teaching physics sections, such as molecular physics and quantum statistics, based on the principle of continuity, incorporating new innovative technologies in organizing lessons, and addressing the underexplored opportunities for developing virtual laboratory sessions related to molecular physics and quantum statistics, further highlights the challenges students face in mastering quantum statistics and probability concepts. The continued reliance on traditional teaching methods in laboratory sessions underscores the need for additional research in this field [5].

Methodology. Concepts of probabilistic and statistical regularities in physics emerged from the development of the molecular-kinetic theory of matter. Prominent physicists, through their studies in molecular-kinetic theory, have clarified the significance of this theory for physics. Works by scientists such as R. Clausius, J. Maxwell, L. Boltzmann, J. Gibbs, A. Einstein, and M. Smoluchowski address the relationship between statistical and dynamic laws, emphasizing that the properties of macroscopic substances and their associated fundamental laws are governed by probabilistic and statistical laws at the microscopic particle level.

This article analyzes and refines the study of micro-phenomena characteristic of micro-objects in quantum and atomic physics using a statistical method grounded in probabilistic and statistical ideas. It recommends integrating sections of quantum and atomic physics into a unified section titled "Quantum Physics", including topics such as the Compton effect, de Broglie's ideas and waves, and Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. The necessity of teaching these topics within a unified physical framework is also substantiated [6].

Moreover, to enhance the quality and effectiveness of education in teaching physical laws, students must be equipped with didactic principles relevant to the subject. Since didactic principles are tied to general goals and challenges, they serve as methods for practically applying fundamental laws and principles of the educational process, shaping the content, form, and methods of learning [7].

From this perspective, the concept of continuity reflects actual development in nature, society, and human thought, describing the connections and causes of development. Since didactics is the theory of teaching and learning, continuity is a didactic principle related to the progression of students' knowledge, skills, and abilities.

Adequate mastery of probabilistic and statistical ideas not only broadens students' knowledge but also effectively contributes to shaping and developing their scientific worldview. This ensures continuity in their intellectual growth and enhances their probabilistic-statistical thinking skills, which are central to their practical activities [8].

Conclusion. The study demonstrates the positive impact of implementing continuity principles in physics education. By ensuring interconnectedness between sections of physics, students' knowledge improves, and their probabilistic-statistical understanding evolves, supported by pedagogical conditions and a learner-centered functional model. Establishing connections between the laws of molecular physics and quantum statistics enhances students' development based on continuity principles, activates scientific thinking, and fosters independent learning skills. The findings underscore the importance of selecting key topics in quantum physics that promote

continuity and align with modern scientific progress, as not all topics require consistent teaching. This approach enhances educational outcomes by employing innovative pedagogical technologies.

REFERENCES

1. Jorayev M., Samatov B.B., Xujanov E.B. Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida fizika fanini o'qitishni statistik metodlar asosida takomillashtirish. O'quv qo'llanma. – Toshkent, 2017. – 281 b.
2. Zakhidov I., Boyturayeva G. Use of Natural Science and Geography materials in Physics teaching //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. B3. – С. 483-487.
3. Matjanov N.S. Kvant fizikani izchillik tamoyili asosida o'qitish // Boshlang'ish ta'lim va jismoniy madaniyat yo'nalishida sifat va samaradorlikni oshirish: muammo va yechimlar. Xalqaro ilmiy konferentsiya, – Toshkent. 2017. –178-179 b.
4. Qo'chqarova M. Molekulyar fizika va kvant statistikasining tanlangan mavzularini izchillik tamoyili asosida o'qitish. Jamiyat va innovatsiyalar Special Issue – 05 (2023), – 240-245 b.
5. Zaxidov I., Abdullajonov B., Bekmirzaev S. Maktabda elektr toki qonunlarini o'qitishda o'quvchilarning ilmiy biliш qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. B8. – С. 1013-1016.
6. Razumovskiy V.G., Bugayev A.I., va boshq. Fizika o'qitish metodikasi asoslari. – Toshkent, O'qituvchi. 1990. – 414 b.
7. Захидов И. О. ТАЪЛИМДА ФАНЛАРАРО БОҒЛАНИШЛАРНИНГ ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИ Алижанов Дилмурод Аъзамжон ўғли.
8. Halliday D., Resnick R., Walker J., Principles of physics (9th edition). Cleverland state university. // Jojn Wiley & Sons, Inc. 2012. Pg.– 1248 .
9. Матжанов Н.С. Вопросы методики преподавания квантовой физики в педагогических вузах // Ўзбекистон Миллий университети хабарлари. –Ташкент, 2018. -№1/2. С.–186-187.